

**Towards Federated, Certified Infrastructures
for Sensitive Data Research in Germany and
Europe with the de.NBI Cloud**

2026

Executive Summary

Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) and Trusted Research Environments (TREs) have emerged as key infrastructural components addressing urgent needs in biomedical research. They combine access control, auditability, and technical safeguards within isolated and use-case-specific computing environments. In the European Union and in Germany, various frameworks have been emerging that will provide broad access to sensitive health data through SPEs, including the European Health Data Space (EHDS) [1], the Gesundheitsdatennutzungsgesetz (GDNG) [2], and the German Social Code (§64e SGB V) [3], which underpins the genomDE [4] initiative. These mandates reflect the growing policy consensus around the importance of secure processing and provide a legal framework for national infrastructures like the de.NBI Cloud [5] to act as authorized processing environments.

Beyond the health domain, the need for SPEs extends to other categories of sensitive data, including geospatial, ecological, and socio-economic information. For instance, datasets related to endangered species locations, critical infrastructure, or vulnerable populations raise comparable concerns regarding unauthorized access, leakage of data sets, and other types of misuse. Accordingly, SPEs are increasingly recognized as essential components not only in biomedical research but also in broader areas of data-intensive science and policy evaluation.

In this paper, we present the current processes, architecture, and development roadmap of the de.NBI Cloud SPE infrastructure, a federated private cloud environment for research composed of nodes certified under ISO 27001 and other comparable security compliance standards. The de.NBI Cloud supports the operation of SPEs through General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [6] and EHDS-compliant access to sensitive data, allowing to integrate technical, organizational, and regulatory safeguards to ensure secure data analysis across a wide range of research domains. We outline the current infrastructure, its alignment with European initiatives such as EOSC & EOSC-ENTRUST [7], as well as ELIXIR [8], and discuss future developments toward a sustainable, scalable, and interoperable national SPE ecosystem.

1. Background

1.1. Terms and Definitions

The terms Trusted Research Environment (TRE) and Secure Processing Environment (SPE) are not globally defined, and to some extent, the terms are also used interchangeably by different sources. Generally, both terms describe an environment where scientists can gain controlled access to sensitive data while implementing technical and organizational measures that provide a sufficient level of data protection.

In the context of the de.NBI Cloud, it is defined as follows: A Secure Processing Environment (SPE) is a highly protected digital infrastructure providing controlled access to pseudonymized sensitive data for secondary research purposes to authorized users. An SPE implements technical and organizational measures to maximize data protection and privacy. An SPE also includes functionalities for data management, data governance, and project management, all within a tightly controlled and compliant environment. The technical and organizational requirements of an SPE are particularly defined by the legal frameworks that are relevant for accessing the sensitive data.

In our view, the “Trust” in TRE is established through the safe operation of a secure processing environment from a technical perspective. However, “Trust” typically also extends to the people operating and working with a TRE. For the sake of simplicity, we will use SPE in the context of de.NBI Cloud to be synonymous with TRE for the rest of this document.

1.2. Legal Mandates for Storage and Processing of Health Data

While SPEs have been used in various contexts for a long time, legal developments at the European and German national levels have mandated the use of SPEs and thus triggered an increased interest in recent years.

The European Health Data Space (EHDS) [1] establishes a legal framework in Europe to regulate broad access to health data for primary (healthcare) and secondary (e.g. research) purposes. Within the EHDS, the use of SPEs is mandated for working with health-related data. Article 73 sets out the fundamental principles for the establishment and operation of SPEs, ensuring secure handling of sensitive information. Key security measures include: 1) Minimizing the risk of unauthorized access to sensitive data, 2) Logging user activities to maintain transparency and security, and 3) Limiting and reviewing user activities to ensure that no personal electronic health data is downloaded from the SPEs. A formal specification on providing and using SPEs in EHDS is currently in development by the TEHDAS2 project [9].

The German Health Data Usage Act (GDNG) [2], in alignment with the EHDS, establishes a legal framework for making health data available for research in Germany. It mandates that data be provided within an SPE, ensuring that health data remains accessible as pseudonymized individual datasets. Within this SPE, appropriate technical and organizational measures must be in place to ensure that applicants limit data processing to what is strictly necessary for their intended use and, crucially, prevent data from being copied outside of the control of the SPE.

In the genomDE Model Project [4], genomic and clinical data from healthcare (oncology and rare diseases) will be made available through designated data services. These services require access control and must ensure, through appropriate technical and organizational measures, that data processing by authorized users is limited to the necessary scope. Data services will thus be deployed within dedicated SPEs.

1.3. Related Projects & Guidelines

The following paragraphs introduce an intentionally limited selection of related European projects and initiatives that have defined SPE and TRE concepts, nomenclature, guidelines, and architecture blueprints with relevance to the de.NBI Cloud SPE environment.

SATRE

The Standard Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) [10] offers a framework for securely managing sensitive data. Drawing on best practices from UK institutions, it standardizes TRE capabilities across key areas, including information governance, computing technology, data management, and essential support functions. This standardization enhances security, streamlines governance, and improves interoperability among TREs.

EGI TRE Working Group

The EGI TRE Working group has published a TRE comprehensive landscape report [11] that sketches the boundaries of SPEs and TREs and identifies common aspects of TREs across different providers mainly in Europe, with a specific focus on future federating capabilities between TREs in the EOSC federation.

EOSC-ENTRUST

The EOSC-ENTRUST project within the HORIZON Europe program aims to create a European network of trusted research environments for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability by jointly developing a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The project combines driver use-cases and SPE providers to develop and evaluate legal and technical concepts and implementations for secure federated discovery and processing of sensitive data. Especially driver project 1, which centers around a human genetic data use-case, combines experiences from the Federated European Genome Archive (FEGA) [12] and European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) [13] and works towards secure cross-border (re-)analysis of national genome data.

Healthy Cloud

The HealthyCloud project [14] was a European Coordination and Support Action that aimed at creating a Strategic Agenda for the Health Research and Innovation Cloud (HRIC). The project addresses the secure and efficient cross-border sharing of health data for research purposes. The project brought together 21 organizations across 11 European countries to align health data use with EU initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and HealthData@EU [15]. Emphasis was placed on understanding the diverse national approaches to health data governance, mapping the fragmented European landscape, and addressing the challenges inherent in building a federated, interoperable infrastructure.

ELIXIR Compute Platform

The ELIXIR Compute Platform [16] places high priority on enabling secure, end-to-end processing of sensitive data to advance life science research. It is developing a comprehensive framework that supports the entire research pipeline—from data discovery to secure analysis, workflow execution, and publication. The framework includes robust mechanisms for access negotiation, data transfer, and result interpretation in protected environments. The platform is also engaging researchers directly through workshops and guidance documentation, making the tools adaptable, transparent, and tuned to real-world research needs.

TEHDAS2

TEHDAS2 (Second Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space) [9] is a joint European project supporting the rollout of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) by creating shared standards and frameworks for accessing and using health data across borders. It helps member states set up Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs) and develop secure, transparent systems for secondary data use.

UK Health Data Research Alliance (HDR UK)

The UK Health Data Research Alliance (HDR UK) has developed a concept for operating TREs [17]. The concept contains guidelines for data custodians and TRE providers to develop processes and create infrastructures. TREs implement the “Five Safes” framework to enable lawful and ethically sound access to sensitive data while ensuring robust technical and organizational safeguards. The “Five Safes” are:

1. **Safe Projects:** Ensures that data use has a clear, appropriate purpose.
2. **Safe People:** Ensures that users accessing the data are trustworthy and have received adequate training.
3. **Safe Data:** Ensures that the data itself is anonymized and treated to protect confidentiality.
4. **Safe Settings:** Ensures that data is accessed in a secure environment, often a controlled and monitored setting.
5. **Safe Outputs:** Ensures that the outputs of the analysis do not disclose sensitive information.

2. The de.NBI Cloud SPE Environment

Since its inception in 2018, more than €50 million have been invested into establishing and extending the de.NBI Cloud infrastructure at its partner sites with modern compute and storage infrastructure. Sustained funding for hardware and personnel is ensured via the de.NBI network funding provided to the de.NBI partners by the German Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFTR) via Forschungszentrum Jülich, as well as contributions of the federal states and contributing research institutions of the network.

To date, the de.NBI Cloud has attracted more than 4,700 users in more than 1,500 projects, not counting indirect users of services hosted by de.NBI Cloud projects. Additionally, Freiburg University operates the European Galaxy server (usegalaxy.eu) as part of de.NBI Cloud, serving more than 140,000 users. In total, the de.NBI Cloud has been cited more than 1,800 times.

Currently, at least 42 projects from ten Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur (NFDI) [18] consortia, including The German Human Genome-Phenome Archive (GHGA) and NFDI4–Health, and three base services (Jupyter4NFDI, KGI4NFDI, TS4NFDI) are using resources of the de.NBI Cloud infrastructure. The de.NBI Cloud currently provides these projects with 47+ TB of memory, 10,500+ cores, 38 GPUs, 470+ TB of block storage, 500+ TB of object storage, and more than 730 active VMs across multiple locations [19].

The de.NBI Cloud supports the processing of sensitive data by providing different services, as well as technical infrastructure and local data processing agreements between the project and hosting site. Data holders may use the de.NBI Cloud for different data access scenarios, creating tailored sensitive processing environments that depend on the specific requirements and framework conditions in which the data is to be accessed.

2.1. Underlying infrastructure

2.1.1. Overall organizational structure and resources

The de.NBI Cloud is a federated, scientific multi-cloud infrastructure operated by German research institutes within the German Network of Bioinformatics Infrastructure (de.NBI). It currently constitutes eight cloud sites, namely at the universities of Bielefeld (operated together with Forschungszentrum Jülich), Freiburg, Giessen, Heidelberg, Tübingen, as well as BIH at Charité, DKFZ Heidelberg, and EMBL Heidelberg. The de.NBI central coordination unit (CCU) is the central executive organ of the network. The CCU approves criteria and minimal standard requirements for a de.NBI Cloud location, the usage policy, and data protection statement after they have been drafted by the Cloud Working Group and approves and enforces collaboration standards. The permanent Cloud Working Group consists of representatives of each cloud site and is responsible for strategic and practical coordination of the de.NBI Cloud governance, federated operation, and coordination. It is tasked by the CCU to develop recommendations and voice opinions on cloud-related topics to direct decisions of the CCU. It can identify and, with approval by the CCU, research topics of strategic or technical interest to the de.NBI Cloud individually.

2.1.2. Project Application Process

The de.NBI Cloud supports project applications from any researcher associated with the public German research ecosystem [20]. Users log in using a single-sign-on authentication and authorization service provided by Life Science RI AAI service [21]. Users belonging to an institution that is part of the eduGAIN federation [22] can readily use Life Science AAI, while other collaborators can sign up using social login providers like ORCID, Google, and others. The authorization component of LS AAI, Perun, provides the necessary technical infrastructure to manage cloud sites, user roles, projects, and project resource allocations. It is also responsible for transmitting the project resource and user mappings to the individual de.NBI Cloud sites.

Responsibility for a project in an organizational and legal sense is assumed by a designated principal investigator (PI), while the project application may be filed on behalf of a PI, pending their approval. Project resource requests are submitted via the central de.NBI Cloud portal,

must be reviewed and subsequently approved or returned for revision. Projects are then assigned to a cloud location with sufficient resources, able to fulfill the project requirements, unless the cloud access committee vetoes the assignment. Applicants, the cloud access committee, and the corresponding cloud site admins are all informed automatically of the status of project applications (see Figure 1). Through technical means, the cloud sites are integrated with an automatic system to provision new projects or to modify existing projects after approval by both the portal and the cloud site.

Application Process for Sensitive Data

Figure 1. de.NBI Cloud project application process for sensitive data projects. The additional step in comparison to a regular cloud project include the creation of SOPs and a data processing agreement with the hosting cloud site.

In the federated setup of the de.NBI Cloud, the single-user account provided via LS AAI, provides access to all services, depending on the allocated project type, e.g., to OpenStack [23], Kubernetes [24], or SimpleVM [25]. This removes the necessity for multiple accounts for different cloud sites or services. Project PIs and administrators are notified in advance about the pending end of their project's lifetime and can opt to file a project lifetime extension request. Similarly, if the allocated project resources are no longer sufficient, the project PI or a project administrator can file a project resource modification request. All requests have a "human-in-the-loop" to check their eligibility and constraints and to support and consult with users, if necessary. The de.NBI Cloud portal enables users to manage their resources and administrators to manage hosted projects, to assess their requested resources, and communicate with

individual users, all members of a particular project, or members of all projects at a cloud site. Regarding the de.NBI Cloud Governance, the portal automates the lifecycle management of projects, thereby facilitating the handling of hundreds of projects by a small number of governance members.

2.1.3. Information security and certification

The de.NBI Cloud federation has established regular technical coordination structures to establish and maintain state-of-the-art technical and operational security across all locations. The cloud sites participate in mutual internal audits of their IT security management systems. The central cloud governance maintains a current inventory of each site's technical and organizational measures (TOMs) and coordinates centralized functions like the user helpdesk, regular staff training for all cloud sites, legal consultations, as well as communication and coordination with local data protection officers. The sites at Bielefeld University (jointly operated with Forschungszentrum Jülich), University of Tübingen, and University of Freiburg also have certified IT security management systems according to DIN EN ISO 27001 [26]. The site at BIH@Charité is developed to comply with the KRITIS [27] requirements of Charité with a split de.NBI Cloud site between public usage and clinical cloud. Depending on future legal requirements in Germany, a certification following the BSI C5 standard [28] may be considered for the de.NBI Cloud sites.

2.2. Organizational and legal processes

Sensitive data processing in the de.NBI SPE follows the general roles and responsibilities defined in the GDPR, the German Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz, BDSG) [29] and the EHDS. As a basis for using the de.NBI SPE, we assume that a data user, e.g. a researcher, submits a request to access a sensitive dataset for processing within the services provided by the de.NBI SPE. The data is made available by a health data holder, which may, for example, be a research institution that collected the data in the context of a study, or a higher-level entity responsible for regulating access to such data. In this context, the health data holder acts as the data controller under the GDPR and the EHDS. The data user applies for access to the health data via the respective Data Access Committee (DAC). Upon approval, the data user also assumes the role of an independent data controller for the specific secondary use purpose. A data use agreement is concluded between the health data holder and the data user, defining the scope, conditions, and obligations of the data user.

The data user can then initiate a project within the de.NBI SPE and agree to the applicable usage and access policies (see Figure 1). The de.NBI SPE may act as a data processor on behalf of the data user, if required. In this role, the SPE may facilitate the transfer of the health data into the secure environment, control data access, provide processing services, and configure the environment according to the project's needs and regulations. To enable this, the de.NBI SPE concludes a data processing agreement (DPA) with the respective health data holders, ensuring compliance with GDPR and EHDS requirements [30].

2.3. Architectural Components

The de.NBI Secure Processing Environment is based on the de.NBI Cloud environment and implements additional technical and organizational processes to provide sufficient data protection features for working with sensitive data. All security-related infrastructure and operations processes are guided by the principles of separation, control, and least privilege.

2.3.1. Technical Measures for Individual Projects

Following these principles, the de.NBI Cloud projects are operated in isolated, virtualized environments (networking, compute, storage), accessible only via encrypted communication protocols and requiring authenticated and authorized access by individually approved project members. Operations on the components of the virtual environment are limited according to a user's group membership within the project. For example, users in the *project admin* group, as nominated by the project PI, can, among other operations, create virtual machines based on pre-defined base images, grant access to other users who are members of the same project and can create and manage storage volumes attached to the virtual machines.

2.3.2. Controlled-Data-Import

The Controlled-Data-Import (CDI) option requires that the data controller provide read access to the sensitive data linked to individual authorized users, their virtual machines and services deployed within the project, but there are no other technical limitations. The authenticated and authorized researcher is responsible for processing and analyzing the sensitive data using the VMs and deployed services, in compliance with the data usage agreement. Here, data usage agreements define and regulate the possibilities for the researcher to export data and regulate the protection of the data. For example, the data usage agreement outlines the obligations and limits for different user groups and usage scenarios (e.g., requiring approval by the project's PI for downloading the data or performing reidentification of pseudonymized data).

2.3.3. Controlled-Data-Export

The *Controlled-Data-Export (CDE)* option implements technical restrictions that prohibit the researcher from downloading data from the cloud project directly. The researcher can move results from the cloud project into an airlock service, which is mounted to a predefined location in the user's home directory for data review. The data controller then needs to validate that the results do not contain any sensitive data and then allow the researcher to download the non-sensitive data results.

2.3.4. Approved-Software

The *Approved-Software (AS) option* restricts the rights of the researcher on the cloud VMs concerning the installation of packages and software. The VMs can be pre-configured with defined tools, so that software like JupyterLab [31] and RStudio [32] are still available for custom data analysis and processing. Packages available via BioConda [33] can be selected by an administrator during creation of a virtual machine at the user's request and will be installed

automatically (pre-approval). General packages for Python [34], R [35] and other programming languages, as well as pre-built Docker [36] images, are provided via a dedicated software artifact repository that allows group-based permissions and virtual repositories, tailored to the project requirements. This component acts as a proxy for the preconfigured software repositories available on the virtual machines for installation by the user (controlled self-service).

2.3.5. No-Direct-Data-Access

One of the features of SPEs is to allow data holders to provide only indirect data access to researchers / data processors for analysis. In this context, the SPE will temporarily hold data and apply researcher's analytics questions, providing the researcher only with the aggregated or otherwise depersonalized results of their analysis.

With the *No-Direct-Data-Access (NDDA)* option, the researcher does not receive direct read access to the sensitive health data. Here, the researcher can only run selected workflows or containers on the data to guarantee that sensitive data will never be exposed to the researcher at all. The non-sensitive results can then be shared with the researcher, for example, using object storage in an automated way, or after manual review and clearance.

2.3.6. Access Control & Auditing

The integration with LS AAI allows further control of access to individual VM or groups of VMs within a project, supporting scenarios where an individual researcher only has browser-based access to a virtual research environment within a VM, or options to provide a selected number of researchers access to the same virtual research environment. In this scenario, LS AAI can be configured to require a second factor for authentication for any user with access to the SPE.

Access to VMs via SSH may be possible in certain SPE scenarios but is also mediated through a dedicated jump host that a) logs access details (date & time, user ID, target VM) and allows for blocking compromised user accounts from accessing VMs.

Now, LS AAI is extending its AAI concept into an AAAI concept within the scope of the EOSC-ENTRUST project that includes further auditing of user login and access events. This will further help de.NBI Cloud SPEs to fulfill legal obligations, documenting access to and processing of sensitive data. Access to VMs by users in violation of the data usage policy of a sensitive data project can be revoked either by the project administrator, PI or the de.NBI Cloud governance. Data security-related events that require involvement of data protection officers and reportable privacy incidents are handled in close cooperation between the hosting cloud site and the de.NBI Cloud governance.

2.3.7. Accounting & Usage Credits

The de.NBI Cloud is currently evaluating the introduction of centralized accounting of resource usage on a per-project basis across sites. This system will allow the assignment of cost models to virtual machine resources, such as virtual CPUs, random access memory, and storage for volumes or objects, as well as special-purpose hardware, such as GPUs. The system is primarily intended to raise user awareness of resource usage by assigning an initial number

of credits to a project that decreases automatically while resources are in use. Users and project administrators will be notified via e-mail when their credits reach certain thresholds. They will be able to file a request via the cloud portal to replenish their credits and thus also have control and awareness over the resources they use. A similar mechanism is already in place for projects approaching their originally approved operational lifespan.

2.4. DARE UK & EOSC ENTRUST Blueprint Architectural Alignment

Figure 2. Architectural subsystems and components of the de.NBI Cloud SPE. This maps definitions from the EOSC ENTRUST year 1 blueprint architecture to their corresponding building blocks in the de.NBI Cloud SPE reference architecture.

The DARE UK Blueprint Architecture [37] and the EOSC ENTRUST year 1 Blueprint Architecture [38] which is derived from the former, divide environments for working with sensitive data into three main zones: the *Research Analytics Zone (RAZ)*, the *Query Management Zone (QMZ)*, and the *Secure Data Zone (SDZ)*. The de.NBI SPE *Project* and *NDDA* environments correspond to the *RAZ* in the blueprint (see Figure 2). Depending on the specific use case, researchers can access services through these environments. The de.NBI SPE manages sensitive data using secured volumes, which corresponds to the blueprint's *Secure Data Zone*. When necessary, sensitive data can be provided in the *RAZ* via controlled data import. Through the *NDDA Environment*, researchers can initiate workloads using containers or computational workflows. These workloads are executed in the *Execution Environment*, which aligns with the *QMZ* in the Blueprint. The de.NBI SPE also supports federation services for AAI and project management but currently does not have an indexing and query service for external discovery of SPE metadata or federated computations.

3. Future Directions

The digitalization of medicine, research, and digital health will continue to advance. Linking patient data, genomic data, data from imaging techniques, molecular information and other data modalities holds great potential to advance personalized medicine and research. AI, machine learning, and big data analysis enable the processing and analysis of these ever-increasing amounts of data, thereby stimulating more data collection and necessitating scalable, cloud-based environments.

Expanding and improving the interoperability of the de.NBI Cloud SPE infrastructure is essential in digital health as central infrastructures are being overwhelmed by the rapidly growing volumes of health data, and networked cloud infrastructures are the only practical solution for efficiency and modern data analysis [39]. Furthermore, all AI diagnostic tools are now being developed in a cloud-native manner. Cloud-based SPEs are therefore not just an option, but rather a structural necessity, being indispensable for digital health applications [40] and other research areas handling sensitive data.

To ensure the continued relevance, scalability, and sustainability of the de.NBI Cloud SPE infrastructure, we will focus on the development of robust governance and business models that support long-term operations. In Germany, public data infrastructures typically rely on mixed funding models, and a diverse set of funding mechanisms usually makes the infrastructure more sustainable and resilient to changes in the funding landscape. Together with internal and external decision-makers, like our funders, the CCU, the Scientific Advisory Board – SAB, and experts from the above-mentioned European cloud projects, and together with users of the infrastructure, we will develop revised business models that are more suitable to the increasing needs for cloud-based processing and the recent developments of legal requirements.

In the rapidly evolving landscape of national and international SPE providers and the growing demand for SPEs, interoperability is a central objective to achieve a functioning overall data ecosystem, both nationally and at the European level. Our efforts will thus require continuing alignment with initiatives such as EHDS, EOSC, and ELIXIR to facilitate cross-border data access and federation. This also involves an evaluation and alignment with the Year two blueprint of EOSC-ENTRUST, which was recently published [41].

Technical scalability will be addressed not only through the expansion of available resources but through integration with hyperscale cloud providers. This will enable elastic resource provisioning and improved support for computationally intensive, large-scale projects.

4. Conclusions

The de.NBI Cloud already provides SPEs in production that align with most of the DARE UK blueprint requirements, which were also adopted and extended by EOSC ENTRUST, and are in turn aligned with EHDS and GDPR legislations, as well as with requirements laid out in recent German legislation for health data.

To date, the de.NBI Cloud already provides an excellent sovereign and proven basis for secure processing of sensitive data for research in Germany, with a focus on local secure data access and processing. Implementing interoperability and federation capabilities for dataset search, discovery, and controlled access will add further value, especially for collaboration partners like GHGA and other projects that soon need access to federating capabilities for health-related sensitive data.

To extend the number and breadth of federated and interoperable sensitive data use-cases using the de.NBI Cloud SPEs, additional sustained funding for expansion of the secure processing and storage infrastructure, software development, user and administrator training, as well as capacity-building is required.

Pending this support, the de.NBI Cloud SPEs can provide a reliable and trustworthy basis also for other German, European and international initiatives in genomic, personalized and individualized medicine, as well as other research domains that handle sensitive data.

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